

Assessment of Some Haematological Profile Among Individuals Exposed to Automobile and Car Paint Chemicals in Owerri

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Abstract

During work periods, workers are faced with a variety of hazards almost as numerous as the different types of work, including chemicals. This study is aimed at assessing the level of haematological, liver enzymes and kidney profile in automobile and car paint in Owerri, Imo State. A cross-sectional study was carried out from month of May to Oct 2024 and all eligible subjects who filled the questionnaire and give a written informed consent for the study period were sampled. The study population consisted of 25 individuals exposed to automobile chemicals, 25 exposed to car paint chemicals, and an equivalent number of age matched healthy individuals who are not occupationally exposed that served as the controls. The procedure was carried out at Federal University Teaching Hospital, Owerri. Blood sample was collected at the ante-cubital vein aseptically and dispensed into the appropriate containers. The samples were analyzed and the results of the tests were analyzed using SPSS version 27. The mean value of PCV (32.87 ± 10.56)%, TWBC (4.54 ± 1.95) $\times 10^9$ /L, neutrophil (42.80 ± 12.96)% and platelet (203.00 ± 57.26) $\times 10^9$ /L was significantly reduced ($p=0.001$, $p=0.000$, $p=0.014$ and $p=0.000$) in Individuals Exposed to Automobile Chemicals when compared to controls (42.98 ± 9.65)%, (7.81 ± 2.28) $\times 10^9$ /L, (51.75 ± 8.66)% and (297.05 ± 89.15) $\times 10^9$ /L. The mean value of monocyte (9.45 ± 4.26)%, prothrombin (14.48 ± 0.54) secs and APTT (37.42 ± 0.49)secs was significantly increased ($p=0.000$, $p=0.000$ and $p=0.000$) in Individuals Exposed to Automobile Chemicals when compared to controls (4.00 ± 1.59)%, (12.44 ± 0.58) secs and (31.50 ± 0.50)secs. There was a non significant increase ($p=0.616$) in the mean value of lymphocyte (45.09 ± 7.91)% in individuals exposed to car paint chemicals when compared to controls (41.85 ± 7.62)%. There was a non significant decrease ($p=0.529$) in the mean value of eosinophil (2.82 ± 1.52)% in individuals exposed to car paint chemicals when compared to controls (2.85 ± 7.62)%. There was a non significant decrease ($p=0.415$) in the mean value of eosinophil (2.75 ± 1.62)% in individuals exposed to automobile chemicals when compared to controls (2.85 ± 7.62)%. Exposure to automobile and car paint chemicals is associated with. Reduced level of PCV, TWBC, Neutrophil, and platelet with increased level of monocyte prothrombin and APTT. But exposure to this chemical doesn't affect the level of lymphocyte and eosinophil. From the result obtained from the study, it can be deduced that automobile and paint chemicals have significant effects on the levels of hematological parameters analyzed.

Keywords: haematological profile, individuals exposed to automobile, car paint chemicals, owerri

INTRODUCTION

Automobile mechanics, gas station pump attendants, and petrol tanker drivers are among the people who handle these products without the necessary protection against their potential harmful effects [3]. In many occupational settings, the ambient environment is a sink of various contaminants that emerge from point and nonpoint sources and cause direct exposure to workers [1]. Those who are occupationally exposed, such as those who work in the petroleum industry, automobile painting, or automobile mechanic professions, are likely to be more affected than their counterparts who do not work in these industries [2].

Automobile mechanics are craftsmen whose job it is to repair malfunctioning vehicles. They work with gasoline, diesel, and other petroleum products that are commonly used for machine operation and internal combustion in automobile engines. These goods have been shown to have serious negative health impacts and are primarily composed of hydrocarbons [4].

The liver and kidneys metabolize and eliminate hydrocarbons and other components of petroleum products, and exposure to petroleum products has been shown to boost the liver's cytochrome p-450 dependent monooxygenase and glutathione s-transferase. The liver may be impacted by prolonged or frequent exposure to kerosene, diesel, and gasoline because they are primarily hydrocarbons. The fuel for operating these machines is purchased and stored in homes and offices where their fumes constitute environmental health hazards especially during refueling [5].

Paint is a coloring substance or mastic compound that solidifies into a film when applied thinly to a substrate. It is most frequently applied on items to give them texture, color, or protection. Numerous studies have demonstrated that solvents used in the paint industry, for instance, are the source of adverse health symptoms affecting the central and peripheral neurological systems as well as other organ systems. Additionally, heavy metals with known hazards are present in some organic and inorganic compounds utilized in the paint industry. Usually, the manufacture of paints involves a wide variety of raw materials that contain heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and chromium pigments, and fungicides such as mercuric oxide in the production process, which can present with medical hazards, some of which are easily recognized and others that may remain undetected for many years [6, 7].

Occupational exposure to chemical agents by automobile painters may be harmful to their health, inflict damage on the genetic material of the cells of male and female workers, or evoke adverse effects on their health [8].

When assessing the hematotoxicity of benzene, a complete blood count (CBC) is a simple and accessible screening tool that provides information about the distribution and quantity of blood cells, specifically the types and numbers of red blood cells (RBC), white blood cells (WBC), and platelets that alert medical professionals to check symptoms like weakness, fatigue, or bruising; it also diagnoses pathologic conditions like anemia; it can reflect acute or chronic infection allergies; and it can indicate clotting issues. An accelerated erythrocyte sedimentation rate may be indicative of inflammation or the presence of a tumor. However, a slow erythrocyte sedimentation rate may occur (eg, in polycythemia vera). Despite the critical role of cytokines in inflammatory conditions, the erythrocyte sedimentation rate still plays an important role in the diagnosis and follow-up of certain inflammatory conditions such as stroke, coronary artery disease, and prostate cancer [9].

Haemostasis is the mechanism that leads to cessation of bleeding from a blood vessel. There are several interconnected steps in this process. Proteins called coagulation factors are present in the blood and are necessary for the healthy development of blood clots. The coagulation system is a highly regulated cascade that ultimately leads to blood clot formation [10]. Coagulation is mostly used for hemostasis, or to halt bleeding from a broken blood artery. A series of actions known as the coagulation pathway result in hemostasis. Rapid healing and the avoidance of spontaneous bleeding are made possible by the complex pathway. Fibrin activation is the result of two routes, intrinsic and extrinsic, that begin independently but converge at a particular location. The ultimate goal is to use a fibrin mesh to stabilize the platelet plug [11,12].

During work periods, workers are faced with a variety of hazards almost as numerous as the different types of work, including chemicals, biological agents, physical factors, and adverse ergonomic conditions. These are responsible for a variety of health consequences [13].

Automobile mechanics and painters are among the workers who are highly vulnerable to the hazardous effects of harmful chemical compounds because of the lack of adequate regulatory and protective mechanisms put in place to prevent exposure to these harmful chemicals. During the repairs of cars and trucks at the workshops, the mechanics are exposed to vapour saturated air which is expelled in the course of washing the vehicle particles with fuel or trying to detect the cause of the faulty engine. This exposure process is repeated as many times the mechanics comes to work and its further exacerbated by the none usage of personal protective equipment. Several studies have shown that chronic exposures to gasoline toxic constituents by automobile mechanics may result in the occurrence of cancer and other adverse health effect [14].

Automobile painters are exposed to paint aerosols in the course of trying to paint a car and these aerosols according to several reports are relatively harmful to the health of these artisans. With increasing demand for cars and truck in Nigeria and the need to beautify these vehicles, the health and wellbeing of automobile mechanics and painters will be at stake cause of the occupational hazard associated with the job.

Work has its positive health-promoting effects, as the financial dividend provides the worker with the basic necessities of life. The aforementioned translates into healthy well-being, job satisfaction, and ultimately, higher productivity. There is, however, a reciprocal and interactive relationship between the workers and the work environment [15].

Occupational hazard is the risk, harm, or danger that an individual is exposed to at the workplace, whereas occupational diseases result from such exposures to the individual. Although these occupational diseases appear to occur less frequently than other major debilitating diseases, there is evidence that they affect a considerable number of people, particularly in rapidly industrializing countries (e.g., Nigeria), hence indirectly impacting on the economy [16].

Occupational exposures to hydrocarbons and heavy metals are important risk factor that can have effect on the physiological metabolism in human's body levels of exposure. This study was carried out due to the dearth in knowledge on the alterations of haematological parameters in automobile and paint chemicals in individuals who are occupationally exposed to the chemicals in Owerri.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was carried out in three automobile Mechanics and Paint Spayers in Owerri, Imo state.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study was carried out from month of May to October 2024 and all eligible subjects who filled the questionnaire and give a written informed consent for the study period were sampled. The study population consisted of 25 individuals exposed to automobile chemicals, 25 exposed to car paint chemicals, and an equivalent number of age matched healthy individuals who are not occupationally exposed that served as the controls. The procedure was carried out at Federal University Teaching Hospital, Owerri. The results of the tests were analyzed using SPSS version 27.

Method of Recruitment

A total of one hundred a subjects 50 occupational exposed workers and 50 controls were recruited for the study. The study participants were given an informed consent form. Subjects who agree to sign was recruited for the study and given a structured questionnaire to fill.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion criteria

- a) Subjects who signed informed consent to participate in the study.
- b) Subjects who were aged 18- 50 years.
- c) Subjects who have worked as automobile mechanic and paint sprayer for one years and above.
- d) Subjects with no history of diabetes mellitus, liver disease, malignancy, high blood pressure, renal disorder, HIV and endocrine disorder.
- e) Subjects who do not smoke.

Exclusion criteria

- a) Subjects who did provide their informed consent to participate in the study.
- b) Subjects who were aged below 18 years.
- c) Subjects who smoked cigarette.
- d) Subjects with medical history of liver diseases, kidney disease, diabetes, hypertension and other chronic illnesses were excluded from this study.

Sample Collection

Five millilitres of venous blood sample was collected at the ante-cubital vein aseptically, 3mls was dispensed into sodium citrate container, 2mls was dispensed into Ethylene Di-amine Tetra Acetic Acid container, The blood dispensed into the EDTA container was stored in a refrigerator at 4°C while the serum was stored in a freezer at -20°C prior to use.

Laboratory Analysis

Haematological parameters determination (BA, BC Series)

Principle

The Mindray autoanalyzer works under the Coulter's principle by using two electrodes. The internal electrode is contained in the smaller container while the external electrode is within the blood sample solution that is found in the bigger container. The vacuum pulls the sample solution through the orifice (small hole). In turn, the cell causes resistance

(electrical) as it passes via the orifice to the current. The recorded resistance is measured and amplified. The amplified resistance is processed and thereafter processed for interpretation into a histogram by a computer.

Methodology

The haematological parameters were determined using mindrary five part haematology analyzer. The blood in the EDTA container was aspirated by the machine and the result displayed on the screen.

Haemostatic parameters

Principle

The CA-101 uses turbo-densitometry and combines the best of both mechanical and optical detection principles. The lamp intensity automatically adjusts to sample turbidity, which means all samples are properly analysed with constant high quality results. Results are automatically calculated for PT and fibrinogen.

Methodology

PT and APTT was determined using CA-101 systmex. The sample from the sodium citrate container was centrifuged at 2500 G for 15 minutes to obtain platelet poor plasma. The sample was dispensed in a cuvette together with the reagent and was incubated before been read by the machine.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 27 (statistical packages for social sciences). All values were expressed as mean± standard deviation. The student-t-test and Pearson correlation was used to detect the difference in the experimental variables. The tests with a probability $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

Table 4.1:

The mean value of PCV (32.87 ± 10.56)%, TWBC (4.54 ± 1.95) $\times 10^9/L$, neutrophil (42.80 ± 12.96)% and platelet (203.00 ± 57.26) $\times 10^9/L$ was significantly reduced in Individuals Exposed to Automobile Chemicals when compared to controls (42.98 ± 9.65)%, (7.81 ± 2.28) $\times 10^9/L$, (51.75 ± 8.66)% and (297.05 ± 89.15) $\times 10^9/L$ ($t=5.41, p=0.001$; $t=4.86, p=0.000$; $t=2.57, p=0.014$ and $t=3.97, p=0.000$).

Furthermore, the mean value of monocyte (9.45 ± 4.26)%, prothrombin (14.48 ± 0.54) secs and APTT (37.42 ± 0.49) secs was significantly increased in Individuals Exposed to Automobile Chemicals when compared to controls (4.00 ± 1.59)%, (12.44 ± 0.58) secs and (31.50 ± 0.50) secs ($t=5.36, p=0.000$; $t=18.19, p=0.000$ and $t=58.98, p=0.000$).

There was a non significant increase in the mean value of lymphocyte (43.75 ± 10.91) % in individuals exposed to automobile chemicals when compared to controls (41.85 ± 7.62)% ($t=0.64, p=0.527$).

As shown in table 4.1 above

There was a non significant decrease in the mean value of eosinophil (2.75 ± 1.62)% in individuals exposed to automobile chemicals when compared to controls (2.85 ± 7.62)% ($t=0.82, p=0.415$).

Table 4.1:1 Mean Value of PCV, Total WBC, Neutrophil, Lymphocyte, Eosinophil and Monocyte in Individuals Exposed to Automobile Chemicals versus Control

Parameter	Subjects Exposed to Automobile Chemicals(n=25)	Unexposed Subject Controls(n=25)	t-value	p-value
PCV (%)	32.87 ± 10.56	42.98 ± 9.65	5.41	0.001
TWBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	4.54 ± 1.95	7.81 ± 2.28	4.86	0.000
Neutrophil (%)	42.80 ± 12.96	51.75 ± 8.66	2.57	0.014
Lymphocyte (%)	43.75 ± 10.91	41.85 ± 7.62	0.64	0.527
Eosinophil (%)	2.75 ± 1.62	2.85 ± 7.62	0.82	0.415
Monocyte (%)	9.45 ± 4.26	4.00 ± 1.59	5.36	0.000
Platelet ($\times 10^9/L$)	203.00 ± 57.26	297.05 ± 89.15	3.97	0.000
Prothrombin (secs)	14.48 ± 0.54	12.44 ± 0.58	18.19	0.000
APTT (secs)	37.42 ± 0.49	31.50 ± 0.50	58.98	0.000

KEY:

PCV: Packed Cell Volume

TWBC: Total White Blood Cell Count

APTT: Activated partial thromboplastin time

P<0.05: Significant

p>0.05: Not significant

Table 4.2

The mean value of PCV (34.56±9.54)%, TWBC (5.11±2.03)×10⁹/L, neutrophil (43.65±13.64)% and platelet (221.67±51.08) ×10⁹/L was significantly reduced in Individuals Exposed to car paint chemicals when compared to controls (42.98±9.65)%, (7.81±2.28) ×10⁹/L, (51.75±8.66)% and (297.05±89.15) ×10⁹/L (t=4.37,p=0.021; t=6.98, p=0.000; t=7.46, p=0.000 and t=4.79, p=0.000).

The mean value of monocyte (8.63±5.11)%, prothrombin (14.96±1.43)secs and APTT (35.65±0.27)secs was significantly increased in individuals exposed to car paint Chemicals when compared to controls (4.00±1.59)%, (12.44±0.58)secs and (31.50±0.50)secs (t=3.96, p=0.000; t=10.56, p=0.000 and t=50.11, p=0.000).

There was a non significant increase in the mean value of lymphocyte (45.09±7.91)% in individuals exposed to car paint chemicals when compared to controls (41.85±7.62)% (t= 0.64, p=0.616).

As shown in table 4.2 above

There was a non significant decrease in the mean value of eosinophil (2.82±1.52)% in individuals exposed to car paint chemicals when compared to controls (2.85±7.62)% (t= 0.74, p=0.529).

Table 2: Mean Value of PCV, Total WBC, Neutrophil, Lymphocyte, Eosinophil and Monocyte in Individuals Exposed to Car Paint Chemicals versus Control

Parameter	Individuals Exposed to Car Paint Chemicals	Control	t-value	p-value
PCV (%)	34.56±9.54	42.98±9.65	4.37	0.021
TWBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	5.11±2.03	7.81±2.28	6.98	0.000
Neutrophil (%)	43.65±13.64	51.75±8.66	7.46	0.000
Lymphocyte (%)	45.09±7.91	41.85±7.62	0.64	0.616
Eosinophil (%)	2.82±1.52	2.85±7.62	0.74	0.529
Monocyte	8.63±5.11	4.00±1.59	3.96	0.000
Platelet (x10 ⁹ /L)	221.67±51.08	297.05±89.15	4.79	0.000
Prothrombin (secs)	14.96±1.43	12.44±0.58	10.56	0.000
APTT (secs)	35.65±0.27	31.50±0.50	50.11	0.000

KEY:

PCV: Packed Cell Volume

TWBC: Total White Blood Cell Count

APTT: Activated partial thromboplastin time

P<0.05: Significant

p>0.05: Not significant

Discussion

Health effects of occupational exposure to automobile and paint chemicals are fairly unfamiliar among certain workers. However, continued exposures for petrol chemicals might be the cause of well-known consequence of bone marrow suppression, hematological lethal effect, and cancer. Petrol containing solvents like benzene cause hemato-toxicity, immune-toxicity, neurotoxicity, and carcinogenicity [17]. Most heavy metals exposure has been reported by various studies to be the cause of renal dysfunction, liver diseases and organ damage [18,].

In this study, the mean value of packed cell volume was significantly reduced in individuals exposed to automobile and car paint chemical when compared to control. The decreased level of PCV might be as a result of the toxic components especially those in petroleum fumes, which have been reported by several studies to change blood chemistry and induce anaemia by causing bone marrow hypoplasia in experimental animals [19,20]. The result from this study is in agreement with the findings of [21] who reported a similar effect on automobile engineers as they stated that benzene and lead are toxic constituents of gasoline. They become activated in the bone marrow and the cytotoxic effects observed are mediated through disturbance in DNA function. The resultant bone marrow depression is characterized by inadequate production of red cell and other formed elements [22,23,24].

With regards to the individuals exposed to paint chemicals, the decrease in PCV may be due to retarded hemopoiesis, destruction or shrinkage of RBC caused by the constituents of paint. The result is consistent with the findings of (10), who worked on the level of RBC and haemoglobin and also reported a signs of anaemia in individuals exposed to paint chemicals [25].

From the result of the current study, the mean value of total WBC and neutrophil was significantly reduced in both individuals exposed to automobile and car paint chemical when compared to control. According to [26] the aromatic hydrocarbons which is present in both automobile and paint chemicals may have contributed to a significant decrease in WBC and neutrophil. The suppression in bone marrow function and the failure in the migration of phagocytic cells due to the continuous exposure to petroleum products could reduce the number of neutrophils in a way that could affect the immune processes of the workers and may make them vulnerable and more susceptible to different infections. This result is consistent with the study reported by [27].

The mean value of monocyte was significantly increased in both individuals exposed to automobile and car paint chemicals when compared to controls. Early exposure to petrol oil which is a common automobile chemical and the natural resins present in paints may have elicited the immune activation and production of monocyte as a defensive mechanism. This is in agreement with the study carried out by [28] who in his report stated a similar finding.

In contrast to the level of monocyte, there was no significant difference in the mean value of lymphocyte and eosinophil in both individuals exposed to automobile and paint chemicals when compared to controls. Eosinophil are mainly elevated when there is parasitic infection while lymphocyte is mainly increased in viral infection, these might be the reason behind the insignificant result in fuel pump attendants. This result is consistent with many different studies that have found that exposure to benzene results doesn't cause a reduction in both circulating B, T lymphocytes and eosinophil in vivo and reduction in mitogen-stimulated lymphocytes proliferation [29,30,31].

In this study, the mean value of platelet count was significantly reduced in both individuals exposed to automobile and paint chemicals when compared to controls decrease is as a result of the interference of toxic elements in petroleum products and resin in paints with the body which affects the blood chemistry which in turn affects the production of platelets [32,33]. The result of the study is in agreement with that of a study, performed in Lagos on 292 workers of petrol filling station with five years duration of employment and consequently in which 146 painters were found with reduced platelet count.

From the result of this study, there was a raised level of prothrombin (PT) and APTT in both individuals exposed to automobile and paint chemicals when compared to controls. The increase is as a result of the alteration in the clotting factors due to the hydrocarbons present in both the automobile and paint chemical, which then leads to a raised PT and APTT. The findings are in line with the result of [34] who reported a similar finding.

Conclusion

Exposure to automobile and car paint chemicals is associated with reduced level of PCV, TWBC, neutrophil, and platelet with increased level of monocyte prothrombin and APTT. But exposure to this chemical doesn't affect the level of lymphocyte and eosinophil.

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